

Original Article

IMPACT OF ENTREPRENEURIAL MARKETING ON SMEs PERFORMANCE IN SOKOTO STATE, NIGERIA

Hamisu Muhammad (Ph.D.) and Abubakar Muhammad

Department of Economics, Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, Sokoto State.

Email: hmtukur1978@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17405516>

Abstract: This study examined the relationship between entrepreneurial marketing and the performance SMEs in Sokoto State, Nigeria, from selected 100 SMEs. Ordinary least squares (OLS) regression was employed for the analysis. The empirical findings indicated a positive and statistically significant relationship between SMEs performance and proactiveness, opportunity focus, innovativeness, value creation, resource leveraging, and customer intensity in Sokoto State. Conversely, the results revealed a negative and significant relationship between risk-taking and SMEs performance. The study concludes that entrepreneurial marketing factors—specifically proactiveness, opportunity focus, innovativeness, value creation, resource leveraging, and customer intensity—are key determinants of SMEs performance in Sokoto State on average. Among other recommendations, the study emphasizes the need for stakeholders and legislators to establish a system for educating both prospective and experienced business owners about entrepreneurship, particularly focusing on SMEs, while also informing new entrepreneurs about the credit opportunities offered by the CBN.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial marketing, opportunity focus, value creation, proactiveness, risk taking, SMEs.

1. Introduction

Entrepreneurial marketing (EM), introduced in 1982, has been defined by several scholars, including Hills and Hultman (2011) and Morris et al. (2002). It is primarily associated with marketing activities in small firms with limited resources, which necessitates the use of creative and unsophisticated tactics. Additionally, EM describes entrepreneurs' unplanned, nonlinear, and visionary marketing actions, highlighting the adaptive and innovative nature of their approaches (Morris et al., 2002). Entrepreneurial marketing (EM) is an organizational orientation defined by seven underlying dimensions: proactiveness, opportunity focus, calculated risk-taking, innovativeness, customer intensity, resource leveraging, and value creation (Morris et al., 2002). This framework

Original Article

positions EM as a new paradigm that integrates the essential elements of marketing and entrepreneurship, viewing marketing as a process that enables firms to act entrepreneurially (Collinson, 2002).

Agunbiade et al. (2020) emphasized that although SMEs are recognized worldwide as instruments for economic growth and development, governments in developing countries are also doing their best through various tremendous efforts and policies that help to either establish or boost the capacity of SMEs. However, despite these efforts, policy thrust, and institutions, SMEs have regrettably fallen short of expectations, regardless of their position as the oldest, simplest, and common practice of business across the world, which largely covers the gap of unemployment, wealth creation, income generation, and standard of living of developing and developed economies (Ishola et al., 2021).

Several researchers have investigated the impact of entrepreneurial marketing on the performance of small- and medium-sized enterprises, and the results indicated a positive relationship between entrepreneurial marketing dimensions and SME performance (Hacioglu et al., 2012; Rashad, 2018; Zahara et al., 2023) while some investigations showed mixed results among the entrepreneurial marketing dimensions (Sadiku-Dushi et al., 2019; Astuti et al., 2018). This indicates that research on entrepreneurial marketing remains inconclusive. There are few studies on entrepreneurial marketing in the study area and Nigeria at large. It has also been observed from previous literature that very few studies have investigated the relationship between entrepreneurial marketing and SMEs' performance in Nigeria, especially in the northwestern part of the country and Sokoto state in particular, necessitating a more robust study in that area. This is the motive that initiated this research to add to the existing literature and close the gap.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Entrepreneurial marketing (EM)

Morris et al. (2002) defined entrepreneurial marketing as the proactive identification and exploitation of opportunities to acquire and retain profitable customers. This approach emphasizes innovative risk management, resource leveraging, and value creation strategies. Combining these elements, entrepreneurial marketing seeks to navigate uncertainties and effectively respond to market demands, ultimately driving business growth and customer loyalty. Entrepreneurial marketing is an organizational orientation comprising seven key dimensions: proactiveness, opportunity focus, calculated risk-taking, innovativeness, customer intensity, resource leveraging, and value creation (Morris et al., 2002). Collectively, these dimensions enable firms to effectively identify and seize market opportunities, strategically manage risks, and foster customer relationships, ultimately enhancing their competitive advantage and driving growth.

2.2 Dimensions of entrepreneurial marketing

2.2.1 Proactiveness

Zahra et al. (2002) defined proactiveness as a process aimed at altering a firm's business environment and its activities, such as predicting evolution, anticipating change, and taking initiatives. Proactiveness is a process that helps to make early preparations to forestall the occurrence of any uncertainty or risk. Prediction helps firms acquire and deploy such resources ahead of competitors to ignite future growth.

Original Article

2.2.2 Opportunity Focus

It involves both the recognition of potential opportunities and their proactive pursuit through marketing actions. The ability to identify and select the "right" opportunities is crucial, as this decision-making process significantly impacts a firm's overall success (Hamel, 2000). Morris et al. (2002) emphasized that recognizing opportunities can significantly enhance organizational performance, especially when firms possess the knowledge to effectively exploit those opportunities. Awareness of available opportunities enables businesses to take timely and appropriate actions, leading to improved outcomes.

2.2.3 Innovativeness

Lumpkin and Dess (1996) defined innovativeness as a firm's propensity to engage its staff in creativity and to come up with new ideas, as experimentation will always result in the development of new products and services. Morris et al. (2002) suggested that managers should continuously seek new operational activities alongside innovations in market segmentation, brand management, and service levels. This focus on innovativeness reinforces a firm's competitive position and enhances its overall performance. Firms can better respond to market demands and drive sustainable growth by embracing change and exploring new avenues.

2.2.4 Value Creation

Morris et al. (2002) argued that value creation is the most critical dimension of EM. Marketers should leverage a combination of resources to deliver enhanced value to customers. Additionally, marketers must identify untapped sources of customer value, allowing them to innovate and tailor offerings that meet evolving needs. This strategic focus on value not only fosters customer loyalty but also drives competitive advantage in the marketplace.

2.2.5 Resource Leveraging

Morris et al. (2004) defined leveraging as achieving more with less effort or resources. They highlight that marketers need the necessary insight, experience, and skills to identify underutilized resources. By effectively recognizing and optimizing the use of available resources, marketers can enhance efficiency and drive better results. This strategic approach enables firms to maximize their market potential and achieve greater impact.

2.2.6 Customer Intensity

A "customer-centric" approach is an innovative strategy aimed at creating, building, and sustaining customer relationships. According to Becherer et al. (2008), driving activities, referred to as forces within the organization, influence customer intensity. These forces help align the company's operations and culture around customer needs, enhancing engagement and loyalty. Organizations can foster stronger relationships and achieve long-term success by prioritizing customer experience.

2.2.7 Calculated risk taking

According to Morris et al. (2004), business operations are prone to risk, especially when organizations attempt to exploit opportunities that require significant resource investment. The uncertainty associated with these opportunities can lead to potential risks because the outcomes are not guaranteed. This highlights the importance of careful assessment and strategic planning to navigate risks while pursuing growth and innovation. Balancing opportunity and risk is crucial for sustainable business success.

Original Article

2.3 Empirical Review on Entrepreneurial Marketing on SME Performance

Sadiku-Dushi et al., (2019) investigated the impact of entrepreneurial marketing (EM) dimensions (opportunity focus, resource leveraging, value creation, risk aversion, proactivity and innovation, and customer orientation) on SMEs in Kosovo. The findings revealed that opportunity focus, resource leveraging, and value creation are positively related and significantly impact overall SMEs performance. However, the study also noted a notable reluctance among respondents to engage in risk-taking, which may impede innovation and proactive strategies. Hendijani and Seyyed (2018) conducted an empirical study to examine the impact of EM on various performance dimensions among Iranian halal food SMEs. Using a correlational descriptive research design, they distributed 384 questionnaires to managers of halal food SMEs producers, selected through a simple random sampling method. Data were analyzed using SEM based on the partial least squares (PLS) approach via Smart PLS 3 software. The study found that EM had a positive and significant effect on market and innovative performance. However, its impact on production performance was not statistically confirmed. Additionally, the results indicated that production, market, and innovative performance collectively contribute to halal food SMEs' financial performance.

Hacioglu et al., (2012) ascertained how entrepreneurial marketing influences firms' innovative performance. Using structured questionnaires, the authors gathered data from managers of 560 SMEs within the Turkish manufacturing sector and applied regression to analyze the data. The analysis reveals significant positive relationships between the innovative performance of firms and several dimensions of entrepreneurial marketing, namely, proactiveness, innovativeness, customer intensity, and resource leveraging. Rashad (2018) investigated the effect of EM dimensions on the organizational performance of SMEs in Jeddah. EM: proactive orientation, calculated risk-taking, innovativeness, opportunity focus, resource leveraging, customer intensity, and value creation. Data were collected through questionnaires administered to a sample of 50 respondents. The findings of multiple regression analysis revealed that the dimensions of opportunity focus, calculated risk-taking, and value creation are positively and statistically significant with organizational performance.

Astuti et al., (2018) explored how to maximize marketing performance in SMEs by examining various dimensions of entrepreneurial marketing, including customer focus, innovativeness, value creation, opportunity focus, proactiveness, calculated risk taking, and resource leveraging, along with their associated marketing strategy clusters. Based on data collected from 130 SMEs in Indonesia, a profile deviation approach is employed to assess the concept of fit. The findings reveal that value creation and opportunity focus have a positive and significant relationship with SMEs performance. In contrast, Customer Focus, Innovativeness, Proactiveness, Calculated Risk Taking, and Resource Leveraging did not significantly affect performance. Ouragini and Lakhali (2024) aimed to deepen the understanding of EM and its impact on firm performance. They conducted quantitative research through a survey involving 328 Tunisian SMEs in the Sousse region. Using STATA software, descriptive and multiple regression analyses were performed. The results indicated that overall firm performance is positively associated with various EM dimensions, including customer focus, innovativeness, value creation, opportunity focus, proactiveness, calculated risk taking, and resource leveraging.

Rezvani and Fathollahzadeh (2020) examined the impact of entrepreneurial marketing on innovative marketing within small- and medium-sized companies that globally produce industrial tools and mechanical parts. The study

Original Article

sample comprised 195 participants selected using a simple random sampling method based on the Cochran formula. Data were collected through a questionnaire and analyzed using SEM. The results indicate that value creation and resource leveraging significantly influence innovative performance. Zahara et al., (2023) investigated the influence of EM on marketing performance through digital marketing capabilities in Palu, Indonesia. The study sampled 197 SMEs and employed path analysis for hypothesis testing using Smart-PLS software. The results reveal that the following dimensions of entrepreneurial marketing: Customer Focus, Innovativeness, Value Creation, Opportunity Focus, Proactiveness, Calculated Risk Taking, and Resource Leveraging, positively and significantly impact both digital marketing capabilities and overall marketing performance.

Hoque et al., (2018) empirically investigated the effects of EM strategies on SMEs performance and the mediating role of OC in Bangladesh. The study employs a structured survey, selecting 384 SMEs owners through random cluster sampling. The hypotheses were tested using the SEM-AMOS package 25.0 based on configuration theory. The statistical results indicate that both EM strategies and OC are significantly related to the performance of Bangladeshi SMEs. Additionally, OC was found to mediate the relationship between EM and SMEs performance, highlighting its critical role in enhancing overall effectiveness. Kakeesh et al., (2024) explored the relationship between EM and business performance among SMEs in the services sector in Jordan, emphasizing competitive aggressiveness as a mediating factor. Data from a sample of 320 service-based companies were analyzed using structural equation modeling with AMOS software. The results reveal a significant positive relationship between EM orientation and business performance, highlighting the importance of this orientation in enhancing the effectiveness of service-based SMEs.

Hanaysha and Al-Shaikh (2022) examined the influence of entrepreneurial marketing dimensions on the performance of SMEs in Saudi Arabia. Using primary data gathered through a structured survey from 153 SMEs, the researchers employed SPSS and the PLS-SEM approach for data analysis. The findings revealed that several dimensions, including customer intensity, value creation, innovativeness, resource leveraging, proactiveness, and opportunity focus, positively and statistically significantly impacted firm performance. Conversely, the study found that the risk-taking dimension had no significant effect on performance. This empirical review underscores the critical role of specific EM strategies in enhancing SMEs performance while challenging the conventional belief regarding the importance of risk-taking in this context.

3. Research Methodology

This study opted to use the quantitative research method, cross-sectional data was used because it is the most suitable for collecting primary data. A structural questionnaire with close-ended questions was used to collect data from the respondents, which comprised employees, owners, managers, and owner/managers. The questionnaires consisted of five Likert scales: strongly agree (5), agree (4), undecided (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1).

The data collected from the administered questionnaire were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics, using SPSS, EVIEWS, and Excel. Descriptive statistics, including reliability and validity provided a foundational understanding of the data. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression techniques and correlation tests were utilized to assess the specifications of the model for inferential analysis. This methodology enabled the

Original Article

evaluation of how variations in the independent variables affect the dependent variable. The application of OLS regression was particularly effective in analyzing the relationships between the dimensions of EM and SMEs performance.

$$PRF = f(PAC, OPF, INV, VLC, RSL, CTI, RST,) \dots\dots\dots (3.1)$$

Where, “PRF” denotes SMEs’ performance, “PAC” denotes proactiveness, “OPF” denotes opportunity focus, “INV” denotes innovativeness, “VLC” denotes value creation, “RSL” denotes resource leveraging, “CTI” denotes customer intensity, and “RST” denotes risk taking. The above equation will be reinstated into the mathematical model.

$$PRF_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PAC_{i-1} + \beta_2 OPF_{i-1} + \beta_3 INV_{i-1} + \beta_4 VLC_{i-1} + \beta_5 RSL_{i-1} + \beta_6 CTI_{i-1} + \beta_7 RST_{i-1} \dots\dots\dots (3.2)$$

Where: “ $\beta_1 - \beta_7$ ” is the coefficient of the parameters to be estimated and “i” denotes the time

varying factor. However, the mathematical model can be restated as econometric

Model, as follows:

$$PRF_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PAC_{i-1} + \beta_2 OPF_{i-1} + \beta_3 INV_{i-1} + \beta_4 VLC_{i-1} + \beta_5 RSL_{i-1} + \beta_6 CTI_{i-1} + \beta_7 RST_{i-1} + \alpha_{t-1} \dots\dots\dots (3.3)$$

4. Results and Discussion

Results of the reliability test

The reliability of the instrument was evaluated using the Cronbach’s alpha, with a minimum acceptable value of 0.70, as recommended by Zikmund et al., (2010). Generally, higher values reflect greater reliability.

S/N	Constructs	Cronbach’s Alpha	Number of Items
1	PAC	0.7	7
2	OPF	0.8	7
3	INV	0.7	7
4	VLC	0.7	7
5	RSL	0.8	7
6	CTI	0.7	7
7	RST	0.8	7
Cronbach’s alpha = 0.8			

Source: Field Survey of 2025

The table presents the reliability results for the relationship between EM and SMEs performance in Sokoto State, Nigeria. According to Zikmund et al., (2010), a minimum Cronbach’s alpha threshold of 0.70 is recommended. If the Cronbach’s alpha value meets or exceeds 0.70, it indicates acceptable reliability for the instruments used in the study. Therefore, the findings demonstrate strong reliability based on the critical value of 0.70 established by Zikmund et al. (2010). Additionally, the results are statistically significant when considering the number of items used for each construct.

Original Article

Results of the Validity Test

S/N	Constructs	Average Factor of Component 1	Average Factor of Extracted Components 2	Average Factor of the Extracted Components 3
1	PAC	0.39	0.44	0.51
2	OPF	0.39	0.44	0.51
3	INV	0.39	0.44	0.51
4	VLC	0.39	0.44	0.51
5	RSL	0.39	0.44	0.51
6	CTI	0.39	0.44	0.51
7	RST	0.39	0.44	0.51

Square correlation matrix = 0.001

Source: Field Survey of 2025

The validity test results are presented in Table 1. The average factor components for each construct in this study exceeded the squared correlation value of 0.001, indicating that the study was valid. The squared correlation matrix value of 0.001 is lower than the average component factors for PAC, OPF, INV, VLC, RSL, CTI, and RST. Consequently, the study can proceed with inferential statistical analysis and interpretation using OLS, which will serve as a robustness check for this research.

Multicollinearity Test

Variables	PRF	PAC	OPF	INV	VLC	RSL	CTI	RST
PRF	1	0.2342	0.4104	0.4151	0.2265	0.4505	0.3853	0.0906
PAC	0.2342	1	0.04667	0.0850	0.1088	0.0298	0.2046	0.1308
OPF	0.4104	0.0466	1	0.1539	0.0156	0.1057	0.1276	0.3355
INV	0.4151	0.0850	0.1539	1	0.1108	0.1121	0.4358	0.2391
VLC	0.2265	0.1088	0.0156	0.1108	1	0.0117	0.0927	0.0668
RSL	0.4505	0.0298	0.1057	0.1121	0.0117	1	0.0906	0.0693
CTI	0.3853	0.2046	0.1276	0.4358	0.0927	0.0906	1	0.0839
RST	0.0906	0.1308	0.3355	0.2391	0.0668	0.0693	0.0839	1

The correlation among the variables in the model is shown in Table 1. Various connections exist between the variables, but the results do not show excessive correlation, as previously suggested. Notably, the coefficient values are quite low, reflecting a weak correlation between the dependent and independent variables. According to the Pearson correlation results, the estimated parameters do not indicate multicollinearity. This is supported by the fact that the multivariate coefficient values for all variables in the study are below 0.7. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis, which proposes the existence of multicollinearity among the variables, is rejected, while the null hypothesis is accepted.

Original Article

Relationship between Entrepreneurial Marketing and SMEs Performance (OLS Regression Results)

Dependent variable: SME' performance				
Indp. Varb.	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	P-Value
PAC	0.0347	0.4052	2.5536	0.0123**
OPF	0.3493	0.2644	5.1021	0.0000***
INV	0.6691	0.2963	9.0071	0.0000***
VLC	0.4725	0.3084	4.7741	0.0000***
RSL	0.2241	0.2052	10.8342	0.0000***
CTI	0.9093	0.2773	10.4914	0.0000***
RST	-0.8683	0.2463	-3.5249	0.0007***
C	-0.5726	0.4079	-8.7578	0.0000***
R ² = 90, Adjusted R ² = 90, F-statistic = 28.8557, F-statistic P-value = (0.0000)				Durbin -Watson = 2.03

Source: Author's Computation, E-Views 9, Note: Significant at 1 % (*), 5 % (**), 10 % (*)**

The results illustrated the relationship between EM and SMEs performance in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The findings revealed a positive and statistically significant relationship between proactiveness and SME performance. Specifically, as a measure of entrepreneurial marketing, a 10% increase (or decrease) in proactiveness corresponds to an approximate 0.03% increase (or decrease) in SMEs performance. This indicates that proactiveness is a crucial factor that impacts the success of SMEs in Sokoto State. The findings are consistent with those of Hacıoglu et al., (2012), Rashad (2018), Sadiku-Dushi et al., (2019), Hanaysha and Al-Shaikh (2022), Zahara, Ikhsan et al., (2023), and Ouragini and Lakhali (2024).

Moreover, the study revealed a positive and statistically significant relationship between EM and the performance of SMEs in Sokoto State. Specifically, a 10% increase (or decrease) in opportunity focus correlates with a 0.34% increase (or decrease) in these businesses' performance. This indicates that opportunity focus, as a component of EM, has enhanced the performance of SMEs in Sokoto State, Nigeria, during the study period. These findings align with those of Hacıoglu et al., (2012), Rashad (2018), Sadiku-Dushi et al., (2019), Hanaysha and Al-Shaikh (2022), Zahara et al., (2023), and Ouragini and Lakhali (2024).

Furthermore, the research indicates a positive and statistically significant relationship between SMEs' innovativeness and performance in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Specifically, as a measure of entrepreneurial marketing, a 1% increase (or decrease) in innovativeness is associated with a 0.66% increase (or decrease) in the performance of these businesses. This demonstrates that innovativeness significantly influences the performance of SMEs in Sokoto State. Innovativeness is a key element of an entrepreneurial approach that can positively affect

Original Article

performance. These findings are consistent with those of Hacıoglu et al., (2012), Rashad (2018), Sadiku-Dushi et al., (2019), Hanaysha and Al-Shaikh (2022), Zahara et al., (2023), and Ouragini and Lakhali (2024).

The research indicated a positive and statistically significant relationship between value creation and SMEs' performance in Sokoto State, Nigeria. Specifically, as a measure of entrepreneurial orientation, a 1% increase (or decrease) in value creation is associated with a 0.47% increase (or decrease) in the performance of these businesses. This demonstrates that value creation significantly influences SMEs performance in Sokoto State. Value creation is identified as a key element of an entrepreneurial approach that can positively affect performance. The findings are consistent with those of Hacıoglu et al., (2012), Rashad (2018), Sadiku-Dushi et al., (2019), Hanaysha and Al-Shaikh (2022), Zahara et al., (2023), and Ouragini and Lakhali (2024).

The study found a positive and statistically significant relationship between EM and the performance of SMEs in Sokoto State. Specifically, a 10% increase (or decrease) in resource leveraging is linked to a 0.22% increase (or decrease) in these businesses' performance. This suggests that opportunity focus, as a facet of entrepreneurial marketing, has improved SMEs performance in Sokoto State, Nigeria, during the study period. These findings are consistent with those of Hacıoglu et al., (2012), Rashad (2018), Sadiku-Dushi et al., (2019), Hanaysha and Al-Shaikh (2022), Zahara et al., (2023), and Ouragini and Lakhali (2024).

The results highlighted the relationship between EM and the performance of SMEs in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The findings revealed a positive and statistically significant connection between customer intensity and SMEs performance. Specifically, as a component of entrepreneurial marketing, a 10% increase (or decrease) in customer intensity is associated with an approximately 0.90% increase (or decrease) in SMEs performance. This suggests that customer intensity is a vital factor influencing the success of SMEs in the state of Sokoto. These findings align with those of Hacıoglu et al., (2012), Rashad (2018), Sadiku-Dushi et al., (2019), Hanaysha and Al-Shaikh (2022), Zahara et al., (2023), and Ouragini and Lakhali (2024).

This study identifies a negative and statistically significant relationship between risk-taking and SMEs performance in Sokoto State, aligning with the study of Sadiku-Dushi et al., (2019). This indicates that risk-taking adversely affected SMEs performance during the study period. The study concludes that an entrepreneurial mindset plays a significant role in enhancing the performance of SMEs in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The analysis indicates that when factors related to EM are effectively aligned, they can lead to positive outcomes for business success.

The regression analysis yielded an R^2 value of 90%, indicating that the independent variables can explain 90% of the variations in SME performance, while the remaining 10% is attributed to factors not included in the model. This reflects a reasonable fit for the primary dataset. The adjusted R^2 value of 90% further shows the model's ability to incorporate additional variables without significantly reducing its explanatory power. Additionally, the F-statistic coefficient of 128.8557 (p -value = 0.0000) is statistically significant, demonstrating a strong overall relationship between the dependent and independent variables. At the 1% significance level, the F-statistic underscores the model's robustness. Furthermore, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.03 indicates no autocorrelation among the variables, reinforcing the findings' reliability.

Original Article

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study examined the relationship between entrepreneurial marketing and SME performance in Sokoto State, Nigeria. This study employed both descriptive and inferential statistics for parameter estimation. Risk-taking, as a measure of entrepreneurial marketing, has a negative impact on the performance of SMEs in Sokoto State, Nigeria, which contradicts the theoretical framework. However, proactiveness, opportunity focus, innovativeness, value creation, resource leveraging, and customer intensity, as indicators of entrepreneurial marketing, positively impact the performance of SMEs. The results of this study have demonstrated that aspects of EM have a major impact on SMEs performance. The analysis demonstrates that when entrepreneurial marketing factors are appropriately matched, they can positively impact SMEs success. SMEs performance in Sokoto State increases with an increase in entrepreneurial marketing. Put another way, stakeholders and policymakers must understand that an entrepreneur needs to be creative, aggressive, and self-sufficient to win the market.

The study also demonstrates that entrepreneurs should possess the requisite knowledge, skills, and talents to succeed. In view of the above findings, the following recommendations were suggested: To significantly boost the performance of Nigeria's SMEs and, in turn, the country's GDP, the researcher recommends that stakeholders and policymakers not only inform entrepreneurs about the loan opportunities offered by the CBN, SMEDAN, NIRSAL, and other relevant institutions but also establish a system for training aspiring and experienced entrepreneurs about entrepreneurship, particularly with regard to SMEs.

References

- Agunbiade, A. K., Afolabi, O. M., and Olaiya, A. L. & Omotayo, G. O. (2020). Assessing sustainability of small-scale business opportunities in Nigeria: Prospect and challenges *KIU Journal of Humanities* ISSN: 2415-0843; 5(1): 57-66
- Astuti, R. D., Afiff, A. Z., & Balqiah, E. T. (2018). Entrepreneurial Marketing and Marketing Strategies of SMEs on Marketing Performance: An Empirical Analysis of Fit. *Pertanika Journal. Social. Science. & Humanities*, 26, 39-54.
- Becherer, R. C., Haynes, P. J., & Helms, M. M. (2008). Exploratory investigation of entrepreneurial marketing in small and medium-sized enterprises: The influence of the owner/operator *Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship*, 20(2), 44–63.
- Collinson, E. (2002). Entrepreneurial marketing: A new small business paradigm In *Proceedings of the 2002 International Council for Small Business (ICSB) World Conference* (pp. 1-15).
- Fard, H. M., & Amiri, S. N. (2018). The effect of entrepreneurial marketing on halal food SMEs' performance. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 9(3), 598-620.
- Hacioglu, G., S. S. Eren, M. S. Eren, and H. Celikkan. 2012. The effect of entrepreneurial marketing on firms' innovative performance in Turkish SMEs. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 58, 871-878.

Original Article

Hamel, G., 2000. *Leading the Revolution*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.

Hanaysha, J. R., & Al-Shaikh, M. E. (2022). An Examination of Entrepreneurial Marketing Dimensions and Firm Performance in Small and Medium Enterprises,” *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 18, pp. 11444.

Hills, G. E. and Hultman, C. M. (2011). Academic roots: Entrepreneurial marketing’s past and present *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 24(1), 1-10.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/08276331.2011.10593412>
<https://doi.org/10.1080/08276331.2011.10593412>

Hills, G. E. and Hultman, C. M. (2011). Entrepreneurial Marketing: Growth of a New Marketing Paradigm in *Handbook of Marketing and Entrepreneurship* (pp. 1-20). Edward Elgar Publishing.

Hoque, A. S. M. M., Awang, Z., & Gwadabe, U. M. (2018). The effect of entrepreneurial marketing on Bangladeshi SME performance and the role of organizational culture: a structural equation modeling. *Journal of Management and Operation Research*, 1(16), 1-21.

Ishola, S. A., & Sulaimon, A. A. & Adebisi, S. A. (2021). Dynamic relationship between sustainable entrepreneurship and value creation by SMEs in Agege local government of Lagos, Nigeria *Journal of Global Economics and Business* October 2021, Volume 2, Number 7, 33-46 ISSN: Print 2735-9344, online 2735-9352

Takeesh, D. F., Al-Weshah, G. A., & Alalwan, A. A. (2024). Entrepreneurial marketing and business performance in SMEs: the mediating role of competitive aggressiveness. *Journal of Marketing Analytics*, 1-24.

Lumpkin, G. T., & Dess, G. G. (1996). Clarifying the construct of entrepreneurial orientation and linking it to performance. *The Academy of Management Review*, vol. 21, no. 1, 135-172.

Morris, M. H., Schindehutte, M., & La Forge, R. W. (2004). The emergence of entrepreneurial marketing: nature and meaning. *Entrepreneurship: The Way Ahead*, pp. 91-115.

Morris, M. H., Schindehutte, M., & LaForge, R. W. (2002). Entrepreneurial Marketing: Integrating Emerging Entrepreneurship and Marketing Perspectives *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 10(4), 1-19.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10696679.2002.11501922>

Ouragini, I., & Lakhali, L. (2024). The impact of entrepreneurial marketing on the firm performance. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 15(2), 6003-6025.

Rashad, N. M. (2018). The impact of entrepreneurial marketing dimensions on the organizational performance within Saudi SMEs. *Eurasian Journal of Business and Management*, 6(3), 61-71.

Original Article

- Rezvani, M., & Fathollahzadeh, Z. (2020). The impact of entrepreneurial marketing on innovative marketing performance in small-and medium-sized companies. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 28(2), 136-148. doi:10.1016/j.jsm.2019.01.004.
- Sadiku-Dushi, N., Dana, L. P., & Ramadani, V. (2019). Entrepreneurial marketing dimensions and SMEs performance. *Journal of Business Research*, 100, 86-99. doi:10.1016/j.jbr.2008.08.016
- Zahara, Z., Ikhsan, Santi, I. N., & Farid. (2023). Entrepreneurial marketing and marketing performance through digital marketing capabilities of SMEs in post-pandemic recovery. *Cogent Business & Management*, 10(2), 2204592. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbm.2012.09.012>.
- Zahra, S. A., & Covin, J. G. (2002). "Contextual influences on the corporate entrepreneurship performance relationship: A longitudinal analysis," *Journal of Business Venturing*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 43-58
- Zikmund, W. G., Babin, B. J., Carr, J. C., Griffin, M., 2010. *Business research Methods* (8th ed.). South-Western Cengage Learning.